

D7.4 Second EPOS ICS system portal integration

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Leader Partner	UKRI (BGS)
Main Author(s):	Daniele Bailo, Keith Jeffery, Matt Harrison, Kuvvet Atakan, Chris Card, Jan Michalek, Alessandro Spinuso, Tomasz Spieznic, Damian Ulbricht, Andy Riddick, Jean-Baptiste Roquencourt
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SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the ICS-C system portal integration. The EPOS ICS-C portal is indeed the front window of a complex system that provides the end user scientific data aggregated from EPOS Thematic Core Services. In addition to this data level integration and in order to guarantee functional and non-functional requirements defined in synergy with the EPOS communities, the portal offers a number of functionalities, for instance a secure layer for accessing the Data portal (namely Authentication, Authorisation, Accounting Infrastructure - AAAI), that are not built from the ground up, but integrated from existing resource provider. This second level of integration, functionality level integration, is exemplified in the case of AAAI and distributed processing.

In the current document we describe how the integration of all assets that compose the EPOS ICS System portal has been carried out. The described work has involved several team from many countries and has created synergies between EPOS technical Work Packages, namely WP6 and WP7, and EPOS community Work Packages, that is to say Wps from 8 to 17.

The description of the strategies for managing, interacting and bringing together such a number of stakeholders with different background and even slightly different cultures cannot be dealt with in the framework of this deliverable. However, it might be considered an added value and high-value hidden achievements of the EPOS enterprise.

1. Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to document the integration of the functionalities provided by components of the EPOS-ICS (EPOS Integrated Core Services), with reference to the current ICS-C architecture (D7.2 - Final Report on EPOS-ICS Architecture), into the main EPOS ICS -C portal.

2. ICS-C Architecture and functionalities

The EPOS ICS-C architecture is described in detail in D7.2 - Final Report on EPOS-ICS Architecture. From a system portal integration perspective what needs to be remarked is what functionalities are integrated and what components/building blocks were used to integrate them. The main functionalities that the ICS-C architecture provides, and that are here discussed, are:

- AAAI, i.e. Authentication, Authorisation, Accounting Infrastructure, that guarantees secure access to EPOS resources and guarantees appropriate authorised access to all EPOS assets, including TCS resources;
- The EPOS Metadata Catalogue integration, with specific reference to the metadata ingestion pipeline and to the queries done on the metadata catalogue
- Graphical User Interface (GUI), i.e. the specific interface between the system and the (human) user. Different type of GUIs and the Data access portal will be discussed, including pre-visualisation and workflow management plans
- Enabling reproducible computing through the provision of a development environment where users can create and evaluate new methods using their workspace data. This include a class of services for the management of such environment and the execution of workflows.
- Hosting Environment will be also discussed, as it is the basis upon which the whole system is built.

A detailed description of the achievement and architectures related to the above topics is reported in the following chapters.

3. AAI and Authorisation

In the framework of EPOS, a general agreement within WP6/7 was reached about the fact that management of AAI should be handled by specialised institutions both for technical and governance reasons. For technical reasons, because in EPOS one of the main requirements is to be able to support and integrate several Authentication Systems, for governance reasons because AAI management also requires to cope with administrative matters (i.e. identifying users and dealing with authorisations) which specialised institutions are already prepared to face.

The AAI hosting institution should be indeed able to provide:

IT authentication: the authentication that the user is the person (in role user) that they say they are; this can be done whether integrating existing AAI IdP or by providing registration features;
EPOS stakeholder authorisation management: it prescribes that EPOS organisation managers should be able to apply specific authorisation schemes to existing users in point (1), so that EPOS “knows” what users are entitled to use what resources.

3.1. AAI technical architecture

In the proposed architecture (Figure 1), AAI is managed by an external EPOS component. This component has the following features:

- it can register new users
- it can integrate existing users from other IdP (e.g. Edugain)
- it enables EPOS managers to assign specific authorisation to specific users
- when users are redirected from the GUI to the AAI component, the AAI component issues a token so that the GUI can act on behalf of the user
- it accepts connection by proxies at ICS and TCS level, that will check that the token is still valid, that the user has appropriate authorisation, session has not expired etc.

Figure 1: architectural view of the interaction between the EPOS-ICS component and the EPOS AAI service

In figure above (Figure 1) the architecture of components in EPOS system are presented. The architecture is kind of micro service approach where the system integrated many existing services. Many of them are developed especially to build EPOS system but others are the legacy services that need to be integrated (TCS services and e-infrastructure/HPC services). Therefore, mine challenge in implementing authentication and authorisation into the EPOS system that provides solution for a chains of API/web services calls.

The relevant standard for this OAuth2 Token Exchange (in mature draft¹). This standard structure the tokens and mechanism to obtain and to validate them in Authentication Service. This solution has been validated, and it appeared that for legacy services and for wider adoption of solution creating an authentication proxy, this is a LUA module in web server, would be helpful solution. The general assumption is that context of authenticated user is transferred to the underlying web services using tokens. Important feature is that tokens can be added to HTTP calls without interfering with semantics of the services itself. They are added as authentication mechanism as addition field in the header.

Like here:

```
Authorization: Bearer TOKEN
```

EPOS AAI prototypes that is based on UNITY-IDM has already implementation of OAuth2 Token Exchange mechanism, so prototype was deployed to support delegation scenario.

3.2.Option for login/register

The following methods are available for logging in or registering to the AAI service:

- EGI CheckIn
- EduGAIN accounts
- TCS standard login (IDPs, LDAP if supported)
- “homeless” users (registration on site)
- Social account

Every method of registering will require completing a user profile with the required attributes.

3.3.User profiles

User profiles are needed in order to understand the context of the user and assign appropriate authorisation schema (Table 1).

Possible user profiles can be as follow:

- first name
- last name(s)
- email (confirmation)
- affiliation
 - can be confirmed by EduGAIN
- researcher status (?)
 - default NO
- EPOS member
 - manually managed with some EPOS authority?

¹ <https://tools.ietf.org/html/draft-ietf-oauth-token-exchange-15>

- special EPOS member groups membership

Likewise, level of authorisation and related (required) attributes have been discussed. In Table 1 a preliminary list of Level of Authorisation is provided. This still needs to be agreed and discussed; this is envisaged to take a long time as it involves different skills and professions (Technical, Governance, Realistic) and the discussion should involve all key EPOS stakeholders.

Table 1: Levels of Authorisation and linked attributes

#	Level	Required attributes	Requirements for user	Rights
0	untrusted (anonymous)	(none)	no email confirmation	just access metadata
1	normal user	user	email confirmation (not confirmed name)	access open resources (e.g. services)
2	resource access (including workflows and sensor networks, TNA?)	user & access	trusted affiliation and name	access open resources and resources that require trusted users
3	access to embargoed resources	users & specific restricted access attribute (e.g. EPOSIPmember)	trusted affiliation, name and user group	access to embargoed resources
4	processing	user & processing	trusted affiliation and user role	access to computational resources
5	admin	admin	manually added to admin group	

3.4. Authentication for Web Services (WS)

All EPOS services will work according to a delegation scheme based on OAuth2. The token will be added to each request from the GUI to any EPOS service including ICS-C components and TCS WSs.

TCS WS Authentication

- Providers may implement authentication and authorization based on OAuth2 token and EPOS AAAI services.

- For legacy systems the provider may use NGINX “proxy” which executes validity of token and selected attributes

3.5.GDPR

AAAI service will be main point of accepting data usage policies informed by the metadata catalog. AAAI provider and ICS provider will guaranty compliance with GDPR. Details need to be designed and additional effort for implementing need to be allocated.

3.6.Ingesting personal data into EPOS catalogue

In order to enable the ICS system to manage user authorisation, the authorisation information can be passed from the AAAI node to the EPOS CERIF catalogue through the token, which should include authorisation metadata.

Authorisation metadata can be of different kinds according to the IdP that was used to authenticate the user, so at some point in the communication between AAAI node and EPOS catalogue, an authorisation metadata mapping procedure is envisaged.

For instance, this mapping procedure might establish that all users from “social accounts” have no rights of downloading datasets but only access to metadata, and that all users from official IdP (like Edugain) are entitled at least to download both metadata and datasets.

The Authorisation metadata ingestion pipeline for AAAI still needs to be studied and designed in detail, but in principle it will be close to the ingestion pipeline described in the “metadata ingestion” chapter.

4. Metadata Catalogue and Metadata Ingestion

4.1. The EPOS Metadata Catalogue

The metadata catalogue, is the key technology that enables the system to manage and orchestrate all resources required to satisfy a user request. By using metadata, the ICS-C can discover data or other digital objects requested by a user, contextualise them (for relevance and quality) access them, send them to a processing facility (or move the code to facility holding the data) depending on the constructed workflow, and perform other tasks. The catalogue contains: (i) technical specification to enable autonomic ICS access to TCS discovery and access services, (ii) metadata associated with the digital object with direct link to it, (iii) information about users, resources, software, and services other than data services (e.g. rock mechanics, geochemical analysis, visualization, processing). The data model used for the catalogue is CERIF (Common European Research Information Format)².

Metadata describing the TCS DDSS are stored using the CERIF data model which differs from most metadata standards in that it (1) separates base entities from linking entities thus providing a fully connected graph structure; (2) using the same syntax, stores the semantics associated with values of attributes both for base entities and (for role of the relationship) for linking entities, which also store the temporal duration of the validity of the linkage. This provides great power and flexibility. CERIF also (as a superset) can interoperate with widely adopted metadata formats such as DC (Dublin Core), DCAT (Data Catalogue Vocabulary), CKAN (Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Framework), INSPIRE (the EC version of ISO 19115 for geospatial data) and others. The metadata catalogue also manages the semantics, in order to provide the meaning of the attribute values.

The use of CERIF provides automatically:

- (a) The ability for discovery, contextualization and (re-)use of assets according to the FAIR principles³;
- (b) A clear separation of base entities (things) from link entities (relationships);
- (c) Formal syntax and declared semantics;
- (d) A semantic layer also with the base/link structure allowing crosswalks between semantic terminology spaces;
- (e) Conversion to/from other common metadata formats;
- (f) Built-in provenance information because of the timestamped role-based links;
- (g) Curation facilities because of being able to manage versions, replicates and partitions of digital objects using the base/link structure;

The catalog is constantly evolving with the additional of new assets (such as services, datasets) but also increasingly rich metadata as the TCSs improve their metadata collection to enable more autonomic processing.

A “metadata baseline” has been established and updated, this provides a profile of key metadata elements in the minimum which would be needed to meet the requirements of the ICS, taking into consideration the heterogeneity of the data and services provided by the TCS. This metadata baseline allows us to select key metadata elements from the metadata provided by the TCSs. The

² CERIF is maintained by euroCRIS <http://www.eurocris.org/cerif/main-features-cerif>

³ <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

baseline will expand over time as we identify other key metadata elements from the communities not currently provided in the baseline and key elements required to offer the more complex assets from the TCSs to end-users (e.g. workflow or TNA (Trans-National Access)).

A mapping from elements of the baseline to the CERIF Model has been created. This mapping enabled the creation of appropriate converters to convert metadata from the TCS to populate the CERIF model.

A series of database views have been created to aggregate and simplify the CERIF Model as a middle layer in the database to enable the ICS Web API to retrieve data from the metadata catalogue as per the baseline concepts.

c

Technologies & Frameworks used:

- SQL
- PostgreSQL – open source Object-Relational DBMS

4.2. Metadata Ingestion from TCS

Metadata collection and maintenance is one of the most challenging activities in EPOS since EPOS Preparatory Phase, when the CERIF standard model was selected as model for the EPOS metadata catalogue (e.g. “D6.1 Final assessment of the EPOS PP”). All resources accessed by means of the ICS-C portal rely actually on good metadata description of the assets (datasets, person, web services and other) provided by TCSs.

Far from being simple, the metadata ingestion process from TCSs systems to the ICS metadata catalogue required the design and implementation of an ingestion pipeline.

The final goal is to have a fully automated ingestion pipeline. At the same time a pragmatic approach which ensures that metadata is effectively ingested needs to be undertaken. Indeed in the EPOS IP context, which includes several stakeholders, different institutions, different IT skills from the TCS communities and - even more importantly - where technical solutions are designed according to communities maturity and project timeline, a certain flexibility is required, so that everybody can get onboard and real integration is achieved.

For the above reason, the pipeline has been designed and will be gradually, iteratively implemented. This implies that while full automation is envisaged, some steps will still require manual human interaction for a transition period which is supposed to last from 2 to 3 years.

The picture below (Figure 2) illustrates the metadata ingestion pipeline.

Figure 2: Metadata ingestion pipeline. Each block is a function in the pipeline. Functions can be implemented by means of one or more software components. A dotted line separates the competences: on the left, the functions are supposed to be carried out by TCS. On the right side, it's ICS responsibility to implement and execute functionalities.

Each block represents a conceptual module with a specific functionality.

In order to define in a clear way responsibilities and collaboration boundaries between ICS and TCS, a (dotted) line has been drawn.

On the left side, metadata provision by TCS is described, according to a number of requirements that have been discussed in the ICS-TCS meetings (F2F, plenary, dedicated TCS meetings etc., full list available in D6.4 M30).

The provision of metadata by TCS is envisaged in the EPOS-DCAT-AP RDF format. EPOS-DCAT-AP is an extension of the DCAT Application Profile (AP) for Research Infrastructures in the environmental domain, with a specific focus on the EPOS Research Infrastructure in the domain of Earth Sciences. It extends the description of datasets, dataset series, equipment and services. It largely leverage on existing models and vocabularies like schema.org. EPOS-DCAT-AP was implemented by defining an RDF syntax that can be used for the exchange of descriptions of spatial datasets, dataset series, and services among communities. It was mentioned by W3C DXWG Working Group as application profile⁴. It is available on GitHub⁵.

EPOS- DCAT- AP extension was used as a metadata transport layer, being simpler for TCS community to deal with an RDF standard rather than write convertors to implement mapping from their (usually flat) metadata standards to CERIF.

In the process of metadata provision, some requirements need to be matched: TCS should indeed guarantee a) Stable web services, b) automatic web service description (WADL or WSDL), c) Metadata linking to Digital Objects, not to landing pages, d) Unique Identifiers for any resource (Persons, datasets, etc). As for the identifiers, some clear decisions were taken: a) EPOS will not mint PIDs, b) they can be provided at Institutional level (GFZ, INGV, UiB, KNMI etc..), c) external services (e.g. EUDAT, EGI, or EOSC) can be a possible solution, d) organisation, in the framework of EPOS, should choose one among the several available (PIC or ISNI).

Once metadata provision is guaranteed by TCS (white TCS block), then each community has three options to provide it (three orange boxes):

⁴ https://www.w3.org/2017/dxwg/wiki/Main_Page

⁵ <https://github.com/epos-eu/EPOS-DCAT-AP/tree/EPOS-DCAT-AP-shapes>

- A) *Web metadata Editor*, that should be used for mapping small amounts of static entities, e.g. Person, Organisation, Services, Projects, Software. Metadata Editor Repo & Docs are available online⁶. Metadata Editor will be updated for automatic ingestion, but the first approach is to use GitHub repository⁷ where each TCS will upload (push) the RDF metadata description;
- B) *Automated tools*, that are aimed at facilitating *bulk mapping* (e.g. datasets, equipment, facilities). Tools can be scripts or programs in various languages (python, Java) for TCS metadata format EPOS-DCAT-AP RDF conversion (e.g. StationXML EPOS-DCAT-AP RDF), as in the example case from WP8⁸. In the future, web services RDF description can be static files programmatically polled by ICS.
- C) *A harvester component* - provided by the ICS IT Team - can be used. It is at the moment in the design phase.

The outcome of this second step is metadata in EPOS-DCAT-AP RDF format. Next steps, under the responsibility of ICS, (on the right of dotted vertical line), deal with two main topics: 1) metadata conversion and ingestion into the CERIF metadata catalogue; 2) duplicate pruning.

In order to achieve this, the design hence include the following steps:

- a) *Validator element*, which ensures syntactic and semantic validation. Beta version of SHACL Validator is available through EPOS WebAPI⁹. The outcome is a qualified RDF output;
- b) *RDF ingestor element*, this takes as input a valid EPOS-DCAT-AP RDF, maps and stores metadata elements into CERIF;
- c) *Normaliser*, which checks if metadata is already ingested and “merges” input entities and attributes with existing data;
- d) *Finally, we have CERIF ingestion*, That is to say the update of tables based on new EPOS-DCAT-AP model.

At the moment of writing the current deliverable, the above described metadata ingestion pipeline is being used. As said, in order to follow a pragmatic approach, some steps are still achieved with the intervention of humans: for instance, once the EPOS-DCAT-AP metadata files have been produced by TCS, they need to be committed to the EPOS GitHub repository (<https://github.com/epos-eu/EPOS-DCAT-AP/tree/EPOS-DCAT-AP-shapes/examples>) and validated by dedicated personnel.

The *normaliser* module is under development. Currently, the implemented functionality of this component includes a duplicate check by verifying a record is not ingested twice; procedures for updating existing records are a work in progress at the moment of writing the current deliverable.

⁶ <https://github.com/epos-eu/Web-Metadata-Editor>

⁷ <https://github.com/epos-eu/EPOS-DCAT-AP/tree/EPOS-DCAT-AP-shapes>

⁸ <https://github.com/Jollyfant/EPOS-TURTLE>

⁹ http://epos.cineca.it/webapi/swagger-ui.html#!/4532V132BETA324532Validation32Service/validatorGetUsingPOST_1

5. Access to EPOS resources

5.1. GUI

5.1.1. Portal Landing Page

The landing page of the ICS GUI has been modified (June 2018) to provide better overview of EPOS portal functionalities for various users (Figure 3). There are four main active buttons to redirect the user to interface with specific information about Data, Research Infrastructures, Transnational Access and Virtual Access to individual TCS portals. There is overview of all TCS WP's icons above the main access buttons and those will provide short description of each TCS when hovering by mouse. Those icons will not be linked to any specific content, just informing the user about contributing communities. The four main button actions are described in following paragraphs.

Data

This button is pointing to the main ICS functional portal (**Data Access**, described in next paragraph) which allows the user to browse, discover, explore and combine datasets provided by TCS WPs.

Research Infrastructures

Redirects users to dedicated website which provides information about contributing infrastructures, their organizational structure and assets. This information is useful for governance, stakeholders and potentially new contributors.

Transnational Access (TNA)

Link to website with overview and short description of available TNA calls/applications. The individual TNA applications will be handled by the TNA call announcer, not by ICS (to be discussed).

Virtual Access

Each TCS community is developing their own portals which suit best their needs and following best practice gained during years of development. The Virtual Access button provides list of all available TCS portals and links to them. This can be useful for scientific users who are interested in single domain data and data products. The TCS portals can provide specific tools and methods of processing which are not yet available via the main ICS Data Access portal.

Figure 3: Landing page. 4 different elements of the page

5.1.2. Data Access

Entry to the data access page(s) is via the landing page (presented above), the primary purpose of the data access page(s) is twofold:

1. to allow the user to gain a quick appreciation of the types and quantities of data available within the EPOS system, via an efficient faceted search and default visualizations (where applicable).
2. to allow the user to collate data discovered in step 1 into self-contained "workspaces" where the data can be worked with further; including visualization or manipulation in dedicated processing environments

5.2. Querying & Pre-Visualisation

5.2.1. Summary

Faceted search is a technique which involves augmenting traditional search techniques with a faceted navigation system, allowing users to narrow down search results by applying multiple filters based on faceted classification of the items. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Faceted_search)

Querying for data is carried out via a faceted search, this will allow the user to narrow down their search results based on the facets delivered to the UI by the EPOS web API. Facets provided by the API include such categories as domains, sub-domains, keywords, organizations. The data structures involved are suitably generic as to allow any hierarchy of facets, this will allow for TCSs to augment the standard facet tree with their own sub-trees.

Extract from a facet hierarchy

- + Seismology
 - ShakeMap input
 - + Volcano Observations
 - Chemical analysis...
 - + Keywords
 - Seismic Waveform
 - Petrology
- ...

DDSS Data, Data products, Software and Services

- <https://www.epos-ip.org/glossary/ddss>

Each "leaf" (most deeply nested) facet has a number of results associated with it, the search results displayed to the user is the logical combination of the selected facets and their child facets. In the case of the EPOS portal the results correspond to DDSS categories, where in turn each DDSS contains a number of "distributions". Each distribution represents an online resource that can be accessed directly through the EPOS portal. Depending on the response type of a distribution the the UI may be able to present a visualization (such as spatial or temporal plot), or may just allow the resource to be downloaded to the users local system.

Example of how facets relate to DDSS categories & distributions

- + Seismology
 - ShakeMap input -> [WP08-DDSS-048]
 - + Volcano Observations
 - Chemical analysis... -> [WP08-DDSS-048]
 - + Keywords
 - Seismic Waveform -> [WP08-DDSS-048]
 - Petrology -> [WP08-DDSS-036]
- ...

Given the extract of a facet tree (above) if the user selected "Volcano Observations" the results displayed would be for (in this case) the single DDSS category "WP08-DDSS-048". The "WP08-DDSS-048" category will have a number of distributions associated with it, hence the search results would look something like:

WP08-DDSS-048	"ddss category"
Primary Seismic Waveform Data	"dataset distribution"

...

If the distribution has a response format, supported by the UI, the UI will be able to provide a visualisation, or at the very least the ability to download the distribution.

5.2.2. User Interface for data discovery

The user interface (Figure 4) for data discovery, via the faceted search, and pre-visualisation of supported distributions within DDSS categories, will be structured as shown in the illustration below.

Figure 4: user interface for data discovery snapshot

Page Navigation area: will allow the user to navigate between the data discovery page and the pages for accessing and working with workspaces.

Faceted Search area: will display the facet tree to the user, as the user selects/deselects facets the results displayed in the results area will be updated.

Results area: lists the distributions, grouped by DDSS that correspond to the selected facets. A distribution can be selected for visualisation, depending on the response type of the distribution it may visualized in one of the following ways:

- Spatial Visualisation: a map based visualisation of the data returned by a distribution.
- Temporal Visualization: a temporal/graph based visualisation of the data returned by a distribution.
- Item List: if none of the other visualizations are supported for a distribution, then it may be displayed as a list of one or more items that will have actions associated with them i.e. download.

5.2.3. Workspaces

Workspaces provide users with a way of grouping together data sources of interest, discovered via the faceted search, for the purpose of further visualisation or processing. A user will be able to have multiple workspaces, with each workspace containing a number of items (added from the faceted search page). The items themselves may represent data sources, such as a web-service, that can be further configured by the user, if this is the case the user will be able to manage multiple differing configurations.

In the same way as the distributions discussed earlier, the items (and their potential configurations) can also be visualized assuming they return a supported type of data. Each type of visualisation will

have a dedicated page where only those entries in workspace that are supported by for that type of visualisation are available for display.

In addition to the visualisation, it is expected that the user will eventually be able to launch processing environments linked to their workspaces. This will allow the user to work with the sources of data listed in workspace in an environment (running remotely) using an appropriate technology stack such as Jupyter notebooks¹⁰ or workflow engines.

The user interface for workspaces (Figure 5) will be broken down into individual pages, each with a specific purpose, such as visualisation spatial data, working with processing environments.

General workspace page

Displays all of the contents for a selected workspace, plus any location information that may be associated with items.

Figure 5: user interface for workspaces

Spatial workspace page

It will display only those items from the selected workspace that are determined to return a data type that is eligible for spatial visualisation (Figure 6).

¹⁰ <http://jupyter.org/>

Figure 6: Spatial workspace page

Temporal workspace page

Will display only those items from the selected workspace that are determined to return a data type that is eligible for temporal visualisation (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Temporal workspace page

Processing environment page

Will display an embedded view of a (remotely running) processing environment created to work with the data sources the user has added to the selected workspace (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Processing environment page

5.2.4. Metadata Catalogue queries

The internal EPOS metadata model is evolving. The new RDF based EPOS-DCAT-AP is a major revision of the metadata model used 12 months before. Recent developments of the EPOS metadata model added new entities, new relations of entities and changed cardinalities of attributes. In summary, these changes call for major changes in the handling of metadata in the CERIF metadata catalogue. Both metadata ingestion into the database and metadata handling in the database views had to be revised. Activities focused on keeping the model dynamic, which is a necessity to be able to react on parallel developing requirements, like the Interim report of the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR data¹¹ or activities that aim to link data and scholarly publications like the FAIR Data Project¹².

The basis for database ingest is the EPOS-DCAT-AP, which is an intermediate RDF/Turtle-based format around the EPOS metadata catalogue. The ingest module transforms the graph-based metadata structures of the EPOS-DCAT-AP into the relational CERIF model. To be able to react rapidly to future changes, the relational database is used in a Triple Store fashion, i.e. RDF resource URIs are the elements that link entities and are stored in the CERIF attribute cfURI of each entity. In addition, the relations of entities and attributes used in the RDF model of EPOS populate the semantic layer of CERIF. The mapping now implements recommendations of the CERIF Task Group, which is to use UUIDs as internal identifiers to link the relational tables. This allows for easier copying of metadata into other CERIF-based metadata catalogues due to unlikely collisions of primary keys of the database tables.

The mapping of EPOS-DCAT-AP to CERIF is based on the DCAT-CERIF mapping of the VRE4EIC project and differs in some details. That is, VRE4EIC makes assumptions on the metadata attributes that require cleaned up metadata collections and VRE4EIC maps to a newly generated RDF representation of CERIF that eliminated identifiers still present in the relational

¹¹ Hodson, Jones et al. (2018), Turning FAIR data in to reality. Interim report of the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR data. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1285272>

¹² <http://www.copdess.org/home/enabling-fair-data-project/>

model that is in use by EPOS. In addition, the DCAT extension of EPOS added and linked elements that are non-existent in DCAT. The mapping for EPOS metadata entities in CERIF is visualised in the following table (Table 2). A more complex mapping is carried out also on attributes, and is reported elsewhere¹³.

Table 2: EPOS-DCAT-AP to CERIF entities mappings

EPOS-DCAT entity	CERIF entity	cfclassscheme:class
<i>epos:Equipment</i>	<i>cfequip</i>	<i>epos:Equipment</i>
<i>epos:Facility</i>	<i>cffacil</i>	<i>epos:Facility</i>
<i>dcat:Dataset</i>	<i>cfresprod</i>	<i>dcat:Dataset</i>
<i>dcat:Distribution</i>	<i>cfmedium</i>	<i>dcat:Distribution</i>
<i>schema:ContactPoint</i>	<i>cfpers</i>	<i>schema:ContactPoint</i>
<i>schema:Person</i>	<i>cfpers</i>	<i>schema:Person</i>
<i>schema:Organisation</i>	<i>cforgunit</i>	<i>schema:Organisation</i>
<i>epos:WebService</i>	<i>cfresprod</i>	<i>epos:WebService</i>
<i>schema:SoftwareApplication</i>	<i>cfresprod</i>	<i>schema:SoftwareApplication</i>
<i>schema:softwareSourcecode</i>	<i>cfresprod</i>	<i>schema:SoftwareSourceCode</i>
<i>epos:Publication</i>	<i>cfrespubl</i>	<i>epos:Publication</i>
<i>hydra:APIDocumentation</i>	<i>cfrespubl</i>	<i>hydra:APIDocumentation</i>
<i>hydra:Operation</i>	<i>cfmeas</i>	<i>hydra:Operation</i>
<i>foaf:Project</i>	<i>cfproj</i>	<i>foaf:Project</i>
<i>skos:Concept</i>	<i>cfclass</i>	-
<i>skos:ConceptScheme</i>	<i>cfclassscheme</i>	-
<i>schema:Service</i>	<i>cfsvr</i>	<i>schema:Service</i>

The developed Web-API accesses the metadata in the catalogue through **database views** that provide easy access to the CERIF entities and are designed to support specific tasks. There are views that define the structure of entities through linking tables, there are views that compile a Dublin Core set of CERIF entities for full text search queries, there are views that are intended to be used as filters (e.g. geographical bounding boxes) and there are views that provide additional information.

The most important detail of the new views is, that metadata are exposed in a label-value style. This decouples the view structure from cardinalities of attributes and additional attributes can easily be added if required. Furthermore, the label-value style views allow to create linking views that cross-reference entities. The linking views allow to traverse the structure of the metadata with SQL

¹³ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Opzvcs0DkmW4XdJFjWI5WImxodU5yQM5Kj43stHzuY/edit?usp=sharing>

commands (i.e. Common Table Expression¹⁴ queries) and content of the metadata fields can be added afterwards by doing an SQL JOIN on the result.

To support their specific tasks the database views are provided in different layouts. Views make use of columns labeled labelclass and labelscheme, that are populated via CERIFs semantic layer, to define how information is related to an entity. There are views of base entities that compile a minimum Dublin Core set, e.g. for person, organisation, product (Figure 9) and others. Information in these views is provided in an entity-id-label-value style, i.e. each row of the views contains the name and ID of a CERIF entity and a labelclass and a labelscheme column describing the relation to a text value or a time range.

entity	id	labelscheme	labelclass	txtvalue	lang	startdate	enddate
Product	053cd812-b1e5-44bf-9dfe-817a30d3b576	... epos	WebService	...	rdf	1901-01-01 00:00:00	2099-12-31 23:59:59
Product	053cd812-b1e5-44bf-9dfe-817a30d3b576	... NULL	cfclassscheme	schema	rdf	NULL	NULL
Product	053cd812-b1e5-44bf-9dfe-817a30d3b576	... NULL	cfclass	dateModified	...	rdf	NULL
Product	053cd812-b1e5-44bf-9dfe-817a30d3b576	... schema	dateModified	...	rdf	2017-04-01 02:00:00	2099-12-31 23:59:59
Product	053cd812-b1e5-44bf-9dfe-817a30d3b576	... NULL	cfclass	WebService	...	rdf	NULL
Product	053cd812-b1e5-44bf-9dfe-817a30d3b576	... NULL	cfclassscheme	schema	rdf	NULL	NULL
Product	053cd812-b1e5-44bf-9dfe-817a30d3b576	... dcat	keyword	ShakeMap,ShakeMapXML_Event,Strong Motion,Seismic ...	en	NULL	NULL
Product	053cd812-b1e5-44bf-9dfe-817a30d3b576	... NULL	cfclass	Seismic waveform	...	en	NULL
Product	053cd812-b1e5-44bf-9dfe-817a30d3b576	... Seismology	Seismic waveform	...	en	1901-01-01 00:00:00	2099-12-31 23:59:59
Product	053cd812-b1e5-44bf-9dfe-817a30d3b576	... schema	datePublished	...	rdf	2017-04-01 02:00:00	2099-12-31 23:59:59
Product	053cd812-b1e5-44bf-9dfe-817a30d3b576	... dct	title	ShakeMap Input XML - Rapid Raw Strong Motion (RRS...	en	NULL	NULL
Product	053cd812-b1e5-44bf-9dfe-817a30d3b576	... dct	description	Resources can be used as input files for USGS Sha...	en	NULL	NULL

Figure 9: Database view “Product” compiling the Dublin Core set of the CERIF entity “Product”. The column “txtvalue” in combination with the column “lang” allows a full text search, it is possible to filter for specific attributes like dates or a title, and the columns “labelclass” and “labelscheme” can be used in combination to trigger a faceted search.

Linking views (see example in Figure 10) glue the base entities together and hold information on the relationship type. The views differ in the structure from the views described before. Here each row describes a relationship of two CERIF entities that are characterized by the labelclass and labelscheme columns.

¹⁴ <https://www.postgresql.org/docs/current/static/queries-with.html>

srcentity	srcid	labelscheme	labelclass	tgtentity	tgtid
Product	508aaade-53b3-44b5-8c84-819edbbd208e	... schema	provider	Organisation	ddcf58d9-905a-487e-a4f6-ee6e1d50229e
Product	58246c9a-e0a7-4fce-bafe-b9983208722b	... schema	provider	Organisation	88cc9c08-6f8c-4921-8451-579937529af6
Product	809ffb2e-fba1-4e36-8228-dcb950c51459	... schema	provider	Organisation	4fe57256-0c5b-4eb0-a186-ef95950fa3bb
Product	ea8224dd-b26d-488a-a781-b6cd39c5fb1c	... dct	relation	Equipment	645c2e32-0dbb-4a71-8b30-3b2ad8b75953
Product	ea8224dd-b26d-488a-a781-b6cd39c5fb1c	... dct	relation	Facility	36fa90ff-3e91-40b9-8c23-d50d8e14dc14
Product	e70a4863-63c7-4ec1-960a-3907570c61a7	... dcat	contactPoint	Person	0ed19fa2-27a7-46f5-9125-24d34e5cb1d7
Product	ea8224dd-b26d-488a-a781-b6cd39c5fb1c	... dcat	contactPoint	Person	0ed19fa2-27a7-46f5-9125-24d34e5cb1d7
Product	e70a4863-63c7-4ec1-960a-3907570c61a7	... dcat	contactPoint	Person	7dec1d10-30d7-4efe-aa29-33c17e9b5ae3

Figure 10: Database view “Product_relation” compiling relations of the CERIF entity “Product” to other entities. The columns labelscheme and labelclass are populated through the semantic layer of CERIF.

All base-entity views share the same structure, which allows for easier combination through SQL UNION statement in queries. Furthermore, all linking views share a same structure which makes it easier to navigate the asset in the database.

Geographical bounding boxes and CERIFs measurement entity are intended to be used as additional filter or to join information to an entity. So the structure of these views has been optimized to be easy join with the other views, i.e. bounding boxes and measurements create two views that compile all spatial coverage or measurement information and contain id and entity name of the linking entity.

In summary, the whole view structure in the database changed from wide views with many columns that compile information of one specific entity type to smaller views in an entity-label-value style. This allows to create queries to the metadata asset that make use of fast relational database operations - i.e. “SQL JOIN” on indexed columns. Furthermore, the view structure will not change when attributes are added to entities.

6. Enabling Reproducible Computing

Here we will introduce the solutions that are being iteratively designed and developed to provide the EPOS ICS Portal with advanced computational services. These have the objective to support interoperability between data, software and computations, enabling users to perform common and shareable procedures, as well as developing new and experimental applications. The system assists the users in basic tasks, such as allocation of computational and storage resources and data-staging. It incrementally accommodates more complex computational scenarios, offering them controls for reproducible science through live-notebooks and reusable workflows.

Figure 11: Notebook Service Story Map. Detailed functionalities are organised by larger tasks. The map reports technical challenges and impact on the different components.

6.1. Agile development

The implementation is part of an extensive and iterative design process. In Figure 11, we show the story map associated with the functionalities and the technical components involved in the different phases of a user’s interactive “Happy Flow”. Prioritisation of developments is also indicated in the map and discussed iteratively within the development team and the other partners, especially those involved into the realisation of the EPOS-ICS portal GUI (BGS) and the provision of computational resources (BRGM).

The integration within the EPOS ICS GUI, not yet achieved at the moment of writing this deliverable, will allow the users to select the data to be processed from one of their workspaces. These have been interactively populated with results of interest, previously obtained by searching the ICS catalogue. Once data is selected, users will launch a processing environment that will be associated with the current workspace and where the selected data will be staged onto (which correspond to the first epic/stories of the story-map). This is achieved via the execution of a dedicated workflow that will download the datasets from the data-provider to remote computational facilities. The target computational infrastructures are required to expose software containerisation and infrastructure orchestration technologies (Kubernetes), to dynamically allocate and prepare the needed resources. Eventually the user is presented with a Jupyter notebook interface that will contain the data of interest and that can be further extended with more libraries and datasets. We foresee the opportunity to apply additional preprocessing workflows on the staged data, before the users will start to develop and evaluate new methods via the notebook. Updates to modules and datasets will be controlled by the user from the workspace of the EPOS GUI.

6.2. Technical implementation and API

All the communication between the EPOS-ICS GUI and the infrastructure will be regulated through an API (Notebook-service API). The specification and implementation of the API (swagger/ Java implementation) is proceeding with regular refinement and demo sessions, according to the Agile development process. In Figure 13 we show a schematic representation of the architecture of the system with the specification of the API methods that regulate the management of the notebooks and the execution of workflows onto target resources. The creation of the notebook generates a new container that will persist until explicit deletion from the users. Each workspace is associated with a persistent storage volume where data will be staged and made accessible to the user in read-only mode to prevent modification of the original data. Updates to previously downloaded data will be traced, and the original data preserved in a dedicated stage-history folder. An additional persistent volume is also generated and will represent the actual working storage, where new results and notebook pages will be saved. Workflows are executed as asynchronous jobs, which can be monitored and controlled from the API. Once the workflow terminates, the job is displaced and the resources deallocated. Support for workflow libraries such as CWL and dispel4py are part of the current developments. These are used for the data staging and preprocessing phase, as well for the realisation of new and experimental application through the Jupyter interface, as depicted in a in Figure 12, where we provide a mockup of the envisaged integration

The image shows a screenshot of the EPOS ICS workspace. On the left, there's a navigation sidebar with 'Discover', 'Active Workspace', 'Workspace Content', 'Spatial Visualisation', 'Temporal Visualisation', and 'Processing Model'. The main area displays a Docker container titled 'NetCDF-combine-ProvenanceDemo'. Inside the container, a Jupyter notebook is open, showing a CWL workflow diagram with nodes like 'Collector', 'ANALYSIS1', 'ANALYSIS2', 'combine1', 'combine2', 'COMBINE10', and 'StoreFile1'. The notebook also contains Python code for data processing and provenance collection. An orange arrow points from the workspace navigation to the text 'Workspace push urls to CWL Tool API'.

Figure 12: Data endpoint are passed from the user's workspace to a CWL workflow job. The workflow downloads the data to a dedicated instance (container) of a Jupyter notebook using authentication delegation mechanisms. Users can then develop their methods on the staged data, for instance, through a workflow library. The example shows the implementation of data-processing workflow for NetCDF data, which includes provenance collection and visualisation. These developments are conducted also in synergy with the H2020 project DARE.

We foresee the computational resources to be managed by different national and European e-Infrastructures that will constitute the EPOS Distributed Integrated Core Services (ICS-D). For this reason we are pursuing a design that will be able to accommodate heterogeneity and technological changes, starting with commonly used infrastructure software and methods abstractions. However, for the development and current integration of the service within the EPOS portal, we rely on the Kubernetes environment provided by the BRGM.

Figure 13: schema of the Notebook API methods and deployment. The API exposes methods for the creation of a notebook instance and the management and execution of workflows. Both actions are associated with a user workspace (`workspaceId`). Users can update their processing environment and create snapshots that are traced and restored on-demand.

6.3. Containerisation and Reproducibility

Thanks to containerisation, special attention is dedicated to portability and reproducibility of the results. For this reason we generate dedicated volumes to store data and maintain staging history that keeps track of the data updates requested by the user through the EPOS GUI. Moreover, by creating snapshots of the notebook's status, we enable users to trace and access the different stages of their progress. Snapshot containers will be generated by the user on-demand or automatically upon the explicit request to update the software modules that they may need for their research. These containers will include notebook pages, information about relevant software modules, raw data and results, fostering the traceable and reproducible management of the users' computational environment over time. In addition to that, the scientific workflows systems should produce extensive lineage information. This should be accessed adopting a set of dedicated tools, for instance such as those developed in the VERCE project.

7. Hosting Environment

The hosting environment is based on the GEUS, BGS, BRGM ICS-C hosting UE chosen proposal, now under discussion. Hosting countries are now undertaking the knowledge transfer process and started to provide hosting facilities available both for software developments and system hosting. System is hosted by CINECA (IT), but the GUI is hosted on BRGM and BGS premises (UK, FR). It is expected that in year 3 of the EPOS-IP project full hosting will be transferred to BRGM and BGS. In the following paragraph we report their current status.

7.1. BRGM Current state

7.1.1. Hardware

As of now, the hosting is only at BRGM with the following equipments :

- Physical server:
 - Operating system : VMware ESXi, 6.5.0, 5969303
 - Reference : Dell Inc. PowerEdge R730xd
 - CPU : 4x Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2640 v4
 - Logical Cores : 40
 - RAM : 383,91 GB
 - NIC : 4 x 10Gbit/s
 - Raw Storage :
 - 5 x 600GB (10K RPM SAS)
 - 2 x 480Gb (SSD SATA 6Gbit/s)
- 2 Datacenter :
 - datacenter 1 : 1 server ESXi
 - datacenter 2 : 2 server ESXi
- Physical commutation between servers : 2x10Gbit/s
- Network isolation through 2 VLANs/DMZ :
 - DMZ EPOS Admin : administration of the VSphere Cluster, and security components
 - DMZ EPOS VMs : Virtual Machines hosting EPOS kubernetes Cluster and other components.

The servers are spread across 2 datacenters in different computer racks.

7.1.2. BRGM Administration components

The physical servers are part of a VMware Vsphere cluster with VSAN enabled.

Version is 6.5 for Vsphere and VSAN.

VSAN is used for hyperconvergence purpose.

The administrations components are :

- VSphere Vcenter virtual machine
- VEEAM Backup proxy virtual machine : for BRGM VMs backup
- ZABBIX Monitoring Proxy virtual machine : for BRGM VM and hardware monitoring
- Kubernetes Administration virtual machine

7.1.3. Infrastructure Service components

- Gitlab Server : sharing EPOS components code

- Gilab Runner : building EPOS components
- Kubernetes cluster : (see following kubernetes chapter)
- F5 LTM/ASM virtual machine : used for load balancing between kubernetes nodes.
- NFS virtual machine : shared storage amongst Kubernetes nodes.

7.1.4. Kubernetes

As of now, the kubernetes Cluster is based on raw Google distribution. So far no choice have been made for the final production between raw Google kubernetes distribution, Red Hat Openshift, Docker EE Kubernetes, VMware PKS, and others.
The installation has been made with Kubespray.

The cluster is composed of :

- 3 masters nodes
- 3 slaves nodes : executing EPOS relevant components
- CPU allocated : 2
- RAM : 4 GB
- OS : CentOS Linux release 7.4.1708 (Core)
- Kernel Version: 3.10.0-693.21.1.el7.x86_64
- OS Image: CentOS Linux 7 (Core)
- Operating System: linux
- Architecture: amd64
- Container Runtime Version: docker://17.3.2
- Kubelet Version: v1.9.5
- Kube-Proxy Version: v1.9.5

The slaves nodes are reachable through F5 LTM virtual machine.

7.1.5. Security

Figure 14: Network scheme representing controller, firewall, load balancing web applications and DMZ zones

The link controller and firewall are hardware appliance clusters (Figure 14).
The Load Balancing component is an F5 virtual machine hosted within EPOS Vsphere Cluster.

7.2.Next steps

What just described are some of the technical details of this ongoing work. Further developments are envisaged, and they are included in the specific development roadmaps of BRGM, BGS and GEUS that are currently under study and developments.

Some of the future work include: a) The F5 VM improvements, so to use them also as a DNS server synchronized with BGS F5 instance, b)secure connection establishment for synchronizing the Metadata database between BGS and BRGM.

8. Conclusions and Future developments

EPOS system portal integration is one of the most challenging task in the EPOS-IP project. As evidenced through this deliverable, an enormous effort has been done in order to follow a rigorous approach that, at the same time, was flexible enough to achieve real results in a pragmatic way. This effort required technical and community building skills and actions. What reported is the most effective way that in EPOS we have found to make a Research Infrastructure work and integrate real scientific DDSS that are scientifically meaningful and useful to scientists. The current deliverable hence demonstrates the achievement of the portal integration while describing at the same time the design and the theoretical approach followed. Of course additional efforts and developments are required, especially for what concerns the topics listed below.

Automation of metadata ingestion pipeline

Metadata Ingestion pipeline requires two main actions: the first one is to fully implement its automation; it will be done with a strong synergy with TCS. The second one is to go through an agile-like re-design phase, in order to take into account emerging requirements. Such actions will be carried out in the remaining months, with the final goal of guaranteeing a clean and correct metadata ingestion for the pre-operational phase.

Implementation of the computational environment and workflows

We will pursue the specification and implementation of the notebook and workflow service API. We will discuss further extension points especially for the communication with the ICS-C catalogue concerning the discoverability and adoption of official libraries and the sharing of new experimental data obtained via the processing environment. The functional and not functional requirements will be discussed in the context of real scientific use cases, evaluating flexibility, fit-for-purpose, reproducibility functionalities and performance of deployment and execution of the system's components. The latter will take into account the exploitation of different computational infrastructures, beyond the current setup at BRGM, by coordinating the access of resources from national and international initiatives, such as EOSC-hub and other cloud providers. Although the overall system is designed to be generic and decoupled from the user interface, we will pursue a user friendly integration within the current EPOS-IP portal, in cooperation with the partners developing its user interface.

Implementation of ICS-D

The ICS-D concept is to extend the ICS-C in a virtualized way with additional computing facilities to support the deployed workflows when their resource requirements exceed those of the relevant TCSs. Additionally, if assets from several TCSs are to be used together it may be convenient to transport them all (after suitable selection and projection of data and selection of software components) to one or more e-Is in order to relieve resource loading on the TCSs and to minimise data transport and latency. This should all be managed by the workflow management component of ICS-C. However, non-functional requirements – restrictions concerning privacy, security, performance, cost, rights etc. – have to be taken into account in the deployment and may preclude the use of ICS-D linked to e-Is for some deployments.

The above requirements and additional ones are currently under study and are being tested and implemented on the basis of some pilots (see D7.6, D7.7).

Following the requirements and pilot use cases, further implementation of ICS-D and CES will be done and their interoperability with ICS-C will be tested and reported.

Inclusion of workflows into the GUI

It is anticipated that the user will manage their workflows via the GUI, with a number of actions being available to them for example: creating a new workflow and seeding it with the contents of a workspace; updating available input data sources; pausing and resuming execution; monitoring resources consumed by the workflow etc. Potentially, each workspace may be associated with multiple workflows or notebooks, as such there will be a view of all workflows and notebooks on a per workspace basis allowing the user to manage them; the users interaction with an individual workflow or notebook will be via an additional view in which the content served by the workflow or notebook will be embedded - the actual content served will depend on the nature of the workflow or notebook.

Final remarks

The afore described per-topic future developments are part of a long term plan that is currently under study and development by the EPOS ERIC ICS-C hosting countries. In order to really implement a working Research Infrastructure, the plan will take into account aspects that go further the technical dimension, for instance legalistic and financial. In addition to this, a particular care will be given to the flexibility in terms of ability to use new technologies as soon as the IT scenario evolves, and in terms of ability of plugging in new components in order to increase the ICS-C portal functionalities.